

EARTH SCIENCES

DEPOSITIONAL CONDITIONS AND PETROPHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PRODUCTIVE SERIES IN THE NEFT DASHLARY AREA

Lala Khalilova

*Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University
Associate Professor, PhD on Geology and Mineralogy
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0411-3216>*

Rahima Musayeva

*Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University
Master student*

Nihad Abdullayev

*Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University
Master student*

Abstract

The study of the petrophysical characteristics of sedimentary deposits is an important tool for reconstructing depositional environments and paleogeographic settings. Parameters such as porosity, permeability, density, water and hydrocarbon saturation, as well as electrical and elastic properties reflect both primary sedimentary features and the influence of post-sedimentary processes. The analysis of these data makes it possible to distinguish lithofacies types, assess the spatial variability of reservoir and sealing strata, and improve the reliability of stratigraphic correlation.

The facies method used in paleogeographic analysis helps to identify hydrocarbon-bearing reservoir rocks and productive horizons, thereby refining patterns of rock distribution and depositional environments.

The aim of this article is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the petrophysical and lithofacies characteristics of the Productive Series in the Neft Dashlary area in order to reconstruct depositional conditions and clarify the patterns of reservoir rock formation. The reconstruction was carried out based on the analysis of well-logging data using the Emery method and cyclostratigraphic analysis. The results show that hydrocarbon accumulations are associated with deposits of the Fasila Suite (FS), the Lower Kirmaky Suite (LK), and the Kirmaky Suite (KS) of the Productive Series. The study revealed that the formation and accumulation of hydrocarbons occurred during progradational, retrogradational, and aggradational stages.

The reservoir properties of deposits belonging to the Balakhany Suite horizons (VII, VIIa, and X) and the Fasila, Upper Kirmaky Clay (UKCa), Upper Kirmaky Sandy (UKS), Kirmaky (KS-2), Lower Kirmaky (LK-1, LK-2 upper, LK-2 lower), and Qala (QaS) Suites of the Productive Series were analyzed. In addition, regression analysis was performed to determine the correlation relationships between the main petrophysical parameters of these deposits.

Keywords: well log section, facies, suite, reservoir rock, depositional environments, Productive Series.

INTRODUCTION

A comprehensive study of oil and gas fields, including cyclic and lithofacies analyses, as well as the investigation of petrophysical characteristics, is a key tool for reconstructing the depositional conditions of sedimentary strata and assessing hydrocarbon potential [5]. The application of these methods enables not only the determination of paleo-geological conditions of rock formation, but also the use of the results to improve the efficiency of hydrocarbon exploration and prospecting.

Lithofacies analysis is the first stage of formation analysis and is aimed at identifying the conditions of rock formation based on diagnostic features. Lithofacies studies play a particularly important role in hydrocarbon exploration, especially where hydrocarbons accumulate in various types of traps (lithological, stratigraphic, etc.). These methods facilitate stratigraphic correlation, forecasting, and the evaluation of cap rocks and reservoir rocks, and also allow the reconstruction of paleotectonic and paleogeographic settings [6].

Under conditions of limited core sampling, the effectiveness of traditional methods may be reduced,

which necessitates the use of indirect approaches, in particular lithofacies interpretation of well-logging data.

Thus, at present, the study of depositional environments is considered a crucial component of exploration activities in oil and gas fields, aimed at identifying not only anticline structures but also non-anticlinal traps. The information obtained about rock genesis makes it possible to predict zones of reservoir development and clay sealing units.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study aims to investigate the lithofacies and petrophysical characteristics of the Productive Series (PS) of the Neft Dashlary area, which allows the reconstruction of depositional conditions and clarifies the patterns of formation and distribution of reservoir rocks.

The Neft Dashlary field is located in the Caspian Sea, in the southeastern part of the Absheron Archipelago, east of Chilov Island, 110 km from Baku (Fig. 1).

The reservoirs of the Productive Series contain rich, multi-layered oil accumulations. From top to bot-

tom, the Productive Series is subdivided into the following suites and horizons: the Surakhany (horizons I₁ and I), the Sabunchi (II, III, IV), the Balakhany (V, VI, VII, VIII, IX, X), the Fasila, the Upper Kirmaky Clay

(UKCa), the Upper Kirmaky Sandy (UKS), the Kirmaky (KS-U, KS-I, KS-2), the Lower Kirmaky (LK-1U, LK-1, LK-2 upper, LK-2 lower), and the Qala (QaS-1, QaS-2, QaS-3, QaS-4).

Fig. 1. Location map of the Neft Dashlary area

The geological section of the Neft Dashlary field comprises 26 oil-bearing horizons and reservoirs. The Productive Series is divided into upper (Surakhany, Sabunchi, Balakhany, and Fasila Suites) and lower (UKC, UKS, KS, LK, QaS) subdivisions.

The Neft Dashlary uplift is located in the pre-Absheron sector of the Absheron–Pribalkhan tectonic uplift belt and represents an independent anticlinal structure [4].

To investigate the structure of the sedimentary section, a set of geophysical well-logging methods was used, including gamma-ray (GR) logging and the spontaneous potential (SP) method. The logging data obtained from well No. 2690 of the Neft Dashlary oil and gas field were interpreted, allowing identification of changes in the lithological composition of the rocks [7, 8]. The reconstruction of depositional environments was performed based on the analysis of well logs using the Emery method [1, 2, 3]. The cyclicity of the section was analyzed using cyclostratigraphic methods based on the collected data. The study focused on the deposits of the Productive Series, namely the Balakhany Suite (VII, VIIa, X), as well as the Fasila Suite, the Upper Kirmaky Clay (UKC, UKCa), the Upper Kirmaky Sandy (UKS), the Kirmaky (KS, KS-2), Lower Kirmaky (LK-1, LK-2 upper, LK-2 lower), and Qala (QaS) Suites.

Subsequently, the reservoir properties of these suites and horizons were analyzed. Correlation between the main petrophysical parameters of these deposits was also examined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Within the framework of the study, reservoirs were identified and their properties determined, including porosity, permeability, and hydrocarbon saturation (Khc), as well as lithology and saturation characteristics of each reservoir. All these data were analyzed together with the results of interpretation using the Emery method and cyclostratigraphic analysis. The results of the analysis are presented below.

The Qala Suite (QaS) mainly consists of clay deposits and sandstones alternating with siltstones and fine-grained sands. The thickness of sandstones and siltstones reaches 20–25 m. The sands are composed of medium- and fine-grained quartz grains, while the clays contain minor sand and moderate carbonate content. Four oil and gas horizons have been identified within this suite. The sandy horizons are separated by clay layers, with thicknesses ranging from 10–25 m to 30–70 m. The lithological characteristics and thicknesses of the sandy horizons and the separating clay layers vary across the area. The sand fraction increases upward within the suite. Aggradation of clays is observed in the QaS (Fig. 2). The calculated average porosity (Kp) is 0.160, the permeability is 0.018, and Khc = 0.101.

The Lower Kirmaky (LK) Suite is composed of quartz sands and sandstones interbedded with medium- and coarse-grained sandy loams and clays, with clays comprising about 30% of the section in the lower and middle parts. The thickness of clay layers separating the sandy horizons ranges from 5–12 m to 20 m. The total thickness of the suite varies from 72 to 135 m, with an average of 110 m. The LK Suite includes the reservoirs LK-1, LK-2 upper, and LK-2 lower. Progradation, aggradation, and progradation–retrogradation are observed within these reservoirs (Fig. 2). Porosity (Kp) ranges from 0.193 to 0.229, permeability from 0.019 to 0.101, and hydrocarbon saturation (Khc) from 0.159 to 0.669.

The KS Suite consists of alternating sequences of fine-grained sands, sandstones, and clays. Downsection, the thickness of sandy layers increases up to 10 m, accompanied by coarsening of the grains. The clay interlayers separating sandy rocks range from 5–10 m thick. In well No. 2690, the KS Suite is represented by one reservoir, KS-2, in which progradation and aggradation are observed (Fig. 2). The thickness of the suite ranges from 165 to 350 m, with an average of 286 m. The KS-2 reservoir is fully hydrocarbon-bearing, with

an average porosity (K_p) of 0.156. Hydrocarbon saturation (K_{hc}) ranges from 0.512 to 0.521, and permeability from 0.030 to 0.034.

The Upper Kirmaky Sandy (UKS) Suite consists predominantly of sandstones and, less commonly, medium- and coarse-grained clayey sands. Low-density sands are present, and sandstones occur in a compacted, well-cemented form. Gravel is also present within the suite. Aggradation is observed in the UKS Suite (Fig. 3). Calculations show that the average porosity (K_p) is 0.217, permeability ranges from 0.063 to 0.096, and hydrocarbon saturation (K_{hc}) is 0.577.

The Upper Kirmaky Clay (UKCa) Suite is composed of a limited amount of sands and sandstones of varied grain size, as well as clays with interbeds of siltstones. In the upper part of the main layer, clays predominate. The sand fraction (up to 40%) is significantly higher than in adjacent deposits and increases upward within the suite. The lower part of the section, 25–40 m thick, consists of sandy deposits and contains oil in blocks II, III, IV, and V. The total thickness of the suite ranges

from 90 to 220 m, with an average thickness of 147 m. Retrogradation, aggradation, and

Fig. 2. Results of Emery and cyclostratigraphic interpretation of the Qala, Lower Kirmaky, and Kirmaky Suites in well Neft Dashlary No. 2690

progradation–retrogradation processes are observed in the UKC Suite (Fig. 3). Porosity (K_p) ranges from 0.154 to 0.161, permeability from 0.030 to 0.034,

and hydrocarbon saturation (K_{hc}) from 0.508 to 0.514.

The Fasila Suite is represented by poorly developed thin interbeds of clay, quartz sands (containing

gravel), and sandstones. The thickness of the suite is 78 m. In well No. 2690, 11 reservoir layers are identified within the Fasila Suite, 3 of which are water-bearing

and the remaining 8 oil-bearing. Aggradation is observed in the Fasila Suite (Fig. 3). Hydrocarbon saturation (Khc) ranges

Fig. 3. Results of Emery and cyclostratigraphic interpretation of the Upper Kirmaky Sandy, Upper Kirmaky Clay, and Fasila Suite in well Neft Dashlary No. 2690

from 0.322 to 0.806, the average porosity (K_p) is 0.217, and permeability ranges from 0.034 to 0.183.

The Balakhany Suite consists of medium- and coarse-grained quartz sands and sandstones with a clayey matrix. The sand content of the section is 50–60%. Within this group, the X, IX, VIII, VIIa, VII, VI, and V sandy horizons are distinguished from bottom to top (Fig. 4).

The X horizon is composed mainly of sands and

sandstones, with a thickness of 30–70 m and an average of 50 m. The depth interval 522.5–540.3 m is water-bearing, while the remainder of the horizon is fully hydrocarbon-bearing. Progradation, progradation–retrogradation, aggradation, and retrogradation are observed in the X horizon (Fig. 4). The average hydrocarbon saturation (K_{hc}) is 0.564, porosity (K_p) ranges from 0.150 to 0.223, and permeability from 0.017 to 0.130.

Fig. 4. Results of Emery and cyclostratigraphic interpretation of horizons X–VII of the Balakhany Suite in well Neft Dashlary No. 2690

The IX horizon consists of fine- and medium-grained sands and sandstones with a clayey matrix. The sand content is 60%, thickness ranges from 38 to 70 m, with an average of 55 m. Six reservoirs are identified within the IX horizon, all of which are water-bearing. Within the horizon, retrogradation transitions upward to clay aggradation (Fig. 4). Permeability ranges from 0.018 to 0.050, average porosity (Kp) is 0.182, and Khc is 0.264.

The VIII horizon consists of fine- and medium-grained sands, sandstones, and clays, and is entirely composed of water-bearing reservoirs. Continuous aggradation is observed in the horizon (Fig. 4). Permeability ranges from 0.042 to 0.060, average porosity (Kp) is 0.224, and hydrocarbon saturation (Khc) is 0.368.

The VII horizon is represented by alternating layers of sand and clay, with sands predominating. Its thickness ranges from 32 to 70 m, with an average of 57 m. Within the horizon, retrogradation at the base transitions upward to progradation. The VIIa sandy layer, 30–70 m thick (average 50 m), is present at the top of the horizon. Both Horizon VII and the VIIa sandy layer are composed of oil-bearing reservoirs. Within the sandy layer, aggradation occurs at the base and top, while progradation dominates in the middle part (Fig. 4). Calculations show that average porosity (Kp) is 0.225, permeability ranges from 0.074 to 0.107, and hydrocarbon saturation (Khc) is 0.666.

At the next stage of the study, a regression analysis of the X horizon of the Balakhany Suite in well No.

2690 was carried out. Graphs of K_{hc} versus K_p and permeability (K_{pr}) versus K_p were plotted and analyzed (Fig. 5). The regression analysis revealed high correlation coefficients between the key parameters: $K_{hc} \leftrightarrow$

K_p ($R = 0.78$) and $K_{pr} \leftrightarrow K_p$ ($R = 0.88$), indicating robust relationships between porosity, permeability, and hydrocarbon saturation.

Fig. 5. Graphs showing (a) hydrocarbon saturation (K_{hc}) versus porosity (K_p) and (b) permeability (K_{pr}) versus porosity (K_p) (for the X horizon of the Balakhany Suite)

Conclusion

A comprehensive analysis of the petrophysical and lithofacies characteristics of the Productive Series of the Neft Dashlary area has shown that the hydrocarbon-bearing deposits comprise horizons VII, VIIa, and X of the Balakhany Suite, the Fasila Suite, UKCa, KS-2, and LK-1, LK-2 upper, and LK-2 lower.

The study of well logging data using the Emery method enabled the reconstruction of the main depositional conditions of the Productive Series in the Neft Dashlary area. The cyclicity of the section was examined using cyclostratigraphic analysis of the acquired materials. Reconstruction of depositional environments indicated that the formation of oil and gas accumulations occurred under progradational–retrogradational and aggradational conditions, which determine the spatial distribution of productive facies and the patterns of reservoir formation.

Regression analysis of the X horizon in well No. 2690 revealed stable correlations between porosity, permeability, and hydrocarbon saturation, thus enabling reliable assessment of reservoir quality.

Therefore, the combination of lithofacies analysis and petrophysical characterization not only allows the identification of highly productive horizons but also facilitates the prediction of their quality, providing a basis for optimizing field development.

References

1. Alekseev, V.P. (2002). Lithofacies analysis: A teaching aid for practical classes and independent work in the discipline "Lithology". Ekaterinburg: Publishing house of the Ural State Geological Survey, 147 p. (In Russian)
2. Belozarov, V.B. (2011). The role of sedimentation models in the electrofacial analysis of terrigenous deposits. *Geology of Oil and Gas. Bulletin of the Tomsk Polytechnic University*. V. 319, 1: 116-123. (In Russian)
3. Emery, D., & Myers, K. J. (1996). Sequence stratigraphy. Hoboken: Blackwell Science Limited, 1st edition. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444313710>.
4. Ismayilov, F., Salmanov, A., Maharramov, B., Shekerov, H. (2024). Oil and gas fields and promising structures of Azerbaijan (Caspian Sea aquatorium). Baku: "MSV Publishing House, pp. 223-254. (In Azerbaijani)
5. Khalilova, L., Khakimova, G. (2023). Clarification of the genesis and lithofacies components of sediments, providing depth in the world of new data. *Proceedings of Azerbaijan High Technical Educational Institutions*. Vol. 30, Issue 07, pp. 316-327. DOI suffix: 10.36962/PAHTEI30072023-316. (In Russian)
6. Khalilova, L.N., Kerimova, K.A. (2022). Facies analysis of Productive Series sediments on the base of well logging data (on the example of the Pirallahi adasy field). *Oil Industry Journal*. Issue 04: 14–18. <https://doi.org/10.24887/0028-2448-2022-4-14-18>. (In Russian)
7. Kvesko, B. B., Kvesko, N. G., Merkulov, V. P. (2020). Fundamentals of geophysical methods for studying oil and gas wells: textbook. manual. - 2nd ed., suppl. M. Vologda: *Infra-Engineering*, 228 p. (In Russian)
8. Maksimov, E.M. Oil and Gas Lithology. (2016). Identification of Lithotypes Based on Well Logging Data. Pp. 26-29. (In Russian)